

DRILLING ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we present the research current state concerning the drilling of different aluminum matrix composites, as well as some significant results. The experimental work was developed considering the machining process characteristics (drilling), through the continuous measuring of the torque and the feed force with an appropriate piezoelectric dynamometer. The wear type was identified and its evolution with cutting time was measured. The hole's surface finish was evaluated with a stylus instrument. We investigated the effect of the cutting fluid in the drilling of a composite type with cemented carbide drills.

Finally, we refer an attempt to obtain a correlation between flank wear evolution and feed force. This attempt has been executed in order to verify if this method can be an indirect one of monitoring the wear and the condition of the drill.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the 70's, the metal matrix composites have been successfully applied in the aeronautic and aerospace industries [1, 2]. In the middle of the 80's, these materials reached the automobile industry and nowadays its use, although not very wide, is starting to be of some importance. Initially, the structural aluminum matrix sheet, reinforced with large fibers, was developed and in the last years research has been specially focused in the aluminum matrix composites with discontinuous reinforcements - short fibers, particles and whiskers of SiC and Al₂O₃ [3, 4, 5].

Most of the parts obtained with metal matrix composites, through different manufacturing processes, namely the processes derived from the casting and bulk plastic deformation (forging and extrusion), have different geometry and they usually need drilling operations with the required dimensional and geometric precision as well as good surface finish.

Although the mechanical properties of the composites have been significantly improved with the introduction of particles or ceramic fibers, they show high hardness and they lead to intensive abrasive wear in cutting tools [6, 8, 9]. The abrasive wear results from cutting with tools which material hardness is lower than the machined material. The SiC and Al₂O₃ reinforcements used in aluminum matrix composites are harder than Tungsten Carbide (WC), the main constituent of hard metal and even than the most of the cutting tool materials, specially HSS. There are exceptions, for instance, Polycrystalline Diamond (PCD), which is approximately three to four times harder.

The problem of drilling these materials was identified after consulting ten databases (USA, England, Japan...). One hundred and fifty three records were selected and an exhaustive bibliographic review was performed, to identify the state of the art. The research by Lane [6,7, 8], Chadwick [9, 13], Heath [9,10, 11], Ginty [13], Ricci [14], Tomac [15], Cronjager [16] and Jawaid [17] are particularly important due to their extension and depth.

2. TESTING CONDITIONS AND MATERIALS

The drilling test program is integrated in a project entitled Machinability of Metal Matrix Composites and has involved until now the execution of about 350 individual tests, including result treatment. Thirty drills have been carefully selected and tested: TiN coated high speed steel (HSS), sintered carbide grade ISO K10/20 (DIN 6535) and polycrystalline diamond tipped (PCD) (DIN 338) drills.

The aluminum matrix composites tested in this work were the following in what concerns matrix and reinforcement: AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp (continuous casting); 6061-T6, 20% SiCp (powder metallurgy - PM) and Al10G1, 20% Al₂O₃f (squeeze casting infiltration of fibrous pre-form). The micro-structures of those three types of composite materials are presented in Fig. 1.

We have used a Kistler piezoelectric dynamometer and its charge amplifier for measuring the cutting forces. Several different programs for data acquisition have been prepared and used based on the -LABVIEW software. They allow the direct record, and simultaneous observation of the evolution of the torque and the feed force in drilling operations. The equipment has been installed in a milling / drilling machine, EASYMILL, with Heidenhain CNC controller, continuous speed control (to 3000 rpm) and 2HP spindle power.

In order to study the drilling behavior of the aluminum matrix composites, we have considered the three following different aspects:

- characterization of the drilling process, by measuring the torque and the feed force, using the referred dynamometer, and calculation of the cutting power and specific cutting pressure.
- identification of the wear mechanisms involved (photographic record in optical microscope) and its quantification using a shop microscope (30x, with micrometric table).
- evaluation of the surface finish of the hole machined in the composite materials.

Finally, we can refer the attempt to obtain a correlation between the evolution of the wear in the drill and the feed force, in order to verify the eventual possibility of indirect control of the tool wear (and condition), for monitoring purposes.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We performed the drilling tests and evaluated some related data: the wear resistance of the drills, the hole surface finish and the influence of the wear on the torque and feed force.

The dominant wear type in MMC drilling has been identified. It is an abrasive form of wear in the drill lip, which can be measured as VB. An example of this wear type is presented in Fig. 2, for an high speed steel (HSS), TiN coated drill, used on a MMC (Al10G1-20% Al₂O₃f) produced by squeeze casting infiltration, and for a PCD drill used on a continuous cast MMC (AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp).

In the drilling operation we have observed that the Al10G1-20%Al₂O₃f squeeze casting infiltration composite produces the least wear (VB_{max}) in the same machining time, for the conditions presented in Fig. 3. It has been possible to drill about 50 cm of composite material, for a VB_{max} = 0,4 mm, using a TiN coated HSS drill. On the contrary, the continuous cast MMC (AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp) gave the greatest wear. Following the same wear criteria, VB_{max} = 0,4 mm, it was only possible to drill about 5 cm, using a cemented carbide K10/20 tool, which is far more abrasive resistant than the HSS one. The 6061-T6, 20% SiCp composite (powder metallurgy) presented similar results (≈ 5 cm), but using a TiN coated HSS drill, corresponding to an intermediate position in abrasivity.

a)

b)

c)

($\approx 250\times$)

Figure 1. Micro-structures of the three types of tested composites. a) AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp (continuous casting) b) 6061-T6, 20% SiCp (powder metallurgy - PM) c) Al10G1-20% Al₂O₃f (squeeze casting infiltration of fibrous pre-form)

Figure 2. Drill lip wear (VB). a) TiN coated HSS drill, after 36 holes (cutting time \approx 2,5 min.)
 b) PCD drill after 80 holes (cutting time \approx 5 min.)

Figure 3. Wear curves for three different composites.

In Fig. 4 it is presented a life curve for cemented carbide tools (K10/20), in the drilling of AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp, continuous cast composite. It has been observed that, under the cutting conditions used for test, the tool life for VB = 0,6mm is not longer than 30 seconds, even in the case of very low cutting speed for cemented carbide tools (20 m/min.).

Figure 4. Life curve for hard metal drills -K10/20-, drilling an AlSi7Mg - T6, 20%SiCp, continuous cast composite.

PCD tipped drills have been used to overcome the problem of the extremely reduced tool life, observed with cemented carbide drills, as indicated by many researchers [9,14,15,16 e 17] who have studied this problem. The test results are presented in Fig. 5. For the PCD tool a maximum lip wear, VBmax. = 0,1mm is observed after 5 minutes of cutting. Using cemented carbide (K10/20) drills, 15 seconds of cutting are enough to produce much more wear (VBmax. = 0,6mm). It must be noted that the feed rate used with PCD drills is only half the one used with carbide drills.

As far as the hole surface finish is concerned, the evolution of the center line average (c.l.a. or Ra) with cutting time is represented in Fig. 6. It has been observed that, under the specific cutting conditions used for test, the carbide drills gave better surface finish than PCD ones. However, the dimensional precision of the holes drilled with carbide tools is not satisfactory, mainly after a VBmax. greater than 0,6mm.

The use of a cutting fluid, Alusol-B 8% in water, in the drilling operation with carbide drills, does not reduce the wear of the tool. However, we have observed a significant reduction of the torque, but not of the feed force.

Finally, we have observed that, as for the machining of conventional materials, the torque (T) is not significantly affected by the flank wear of the drill. On the contrary, it has been possible to establish a good correlation between the evolution of the feed force (Ff) and the maximum value of the wear in the flank face of the tool (VBmax). In Fig. 7, we present the correlation obtained in the drilling of the AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp - continuous cast composite, using a PCD drill.

Figure 5. Wear curves for PCD and K10/20 drills, when drilling AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp composite.

Figure 7. Evolution of the torque (T) and feed force (Ff) with the wear (VBmax.) for a PCD drill, working an AlSi7Mg -T6, 20% SiCp composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have observed that the Al10G1-20%Al₂O₃f composite (squeeze casting infiltration), produces the least wear in the drills. It is possible to drill 50cm of composite material, with a VBmax = 0,4mm, using a TiN coated HSS drill. On the contrary, the AlSi7Mg - T6, 20% SiCp continuous cast composite produced the greatest wear. For a VBmax = 0,4mm it was only possible to drill about 5cm, using a K10/20 carbide drill. The 6061-T6, 20% SiCp PM composite, presented similar values, but using a TiN coated HSS drill. As far as the machinability is concerned this result places the PM composite in an intermediate position.

In the AlSi7Mg-T6, 20% SiCp continuous cast composite, it has been observed, for the cutting conditions used, that the tool life, for a VBmax = 0,6mm is not longer than 30 seconds, even with very small cutting speed (20 m/min. for a carbide tool). The volume of composite removed in this operation is about 4,3 cm³/mm of VBmax, for a 5mm diameter drill. Using PCD, one can get, for a VBmax = 0,1mm, about 5 minutes of cutting time. With the same drill diameter the total composite volume removed is about 200 cm³/mm of VBmax, what means 46,5 times greater.

A better surface finish is obtained using K10/20 carbide drills, than using PCD tools. However, it must be noted, that the last ones have been tested using a very low cutting speed for this material (40m/min.). In addition, the dimensional precision of the holes, drilled with carbide tools, is not good enough.

Finally, it has been possible to establish a good correlation between the evolution of the feed force (Ff) and maximum wear value on the tool lip (VBmax). This observation corresponds to a clear indication that this measure might be used as an indirect way to control the wear of the tool, for monitoring purposes.

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